

A Dynamical Mass for the Planetary-Mass Companion FW Tau C/b: An ALMA Feasibility Study

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Abstract

We present the results of simulated ALMA observations of the 100-200 M_{\oplus} “circum-companion” disk orbiting FW Tau C/b, a wide (~ 300 AU) planetary-mass companion to the binary M6 dwarf FW Tau A/B. These simulations demonstrated that it would be possible to determine the mass of FW Tau C/b by measuring the disk’s rotation and the assumption of Keplerian rotation. Doing so would in turn resolve the question of whether FW Tau C/b is a planet or Brown Dwarf. Building on prior observations performed by Andrews and Williams (2005) and Kraus et al. (2014) along with evolutionary models developed by Chabrier et al (2000), we simulated two fiducial scenarios that represent the possible range of host masses—that of a $.095 M_{\odot}$ brown dwarf largely occluded by a nearly edge-on ($i = 85^{\circ}$) disk and that of a $.01 M_{\odot}$ planet with a more typical viewing geometry ($i = 60^{\circ}$). We generated synthetic position-position-velocity data cubes of these models that mimic realistic ALMA observations in cycle 3. A comparison with cases that vary the fiducial M_c by 50% clearly demonstrates ALMA’s ability to differentiate between cases with varying mass, and indicate that future observations should yield a precise dynamical mass for FW Tau C/b.

1 Introduction

In recent years, astronomers have begun to discover and catalogue a new and taxonomically challenging type of object orbiting distant stars. Originally noticed in wide-field photometric surveys, a number

of these so-called Planetary-Mass Companions have been confirmed by followup observations to be orbiting stars at vast distances—all the way from typical planetary semimajor axes (1-50 AU) out to improbable separations on the order of hundreds, or even thousands, of AU (Naud, et al., 2014). As our current understanding of planet formation is based on the idea of leftover material from the star formation process condensing into a tight disk around the star which then fragments into planets, these objects do not fit at all well into existing models. Further complicating the situation is the high mass of most PMC’s, which often skirt the already-vague distinction between high-mass planets and low-mass stars or brown dwarfs (typically taken as the Deuterium-burning limit, $13 M_{Jupiter}$ (Speigel, et al., 2010)). Theories on PMC formation rely upon complex models of gravitational interactions ejecting close-in planets or of fragmenting molecular cloud collapse creating a substellar object near a young star. However, these theories have thus far been difficult to prove, and PMC formation remains a mystery.

PMC’s are perhaps most interesting simply because they are so poorly understood. However, further study of them could lead to a more complete understanding of the mechanisms behind star and planet formation, not to mention helping us to further define (or revise the definition of) the distinction between planet and star. Observations of PMCs could also be used as a testing ground for technology designed for observation of more conventional exoplanets. In recent years the rate of discovery of extrasolar planets has skyrocketed, largely due to the use of the transit and doppler shift methods, as well as (to a lesser extent) observations of gravitational microlensing. One area that has met with very limited success, however, is direct photometric observations of exoplanets, since the planets are many orders of magnitude dimmer than their host stars, and the angular separation between planet and star is generally minuscule at best. At angular separations often on the scale of arcseconds, PMCs could be targeted by telescopes that would then go on to attempt more difficult observations of planets closer in to their stars.

The focus of our study was FW Tau C/b, a PMC first noted by White & Ghez (2001) in *HST* images. in followup observations performed in 2014 by Kraus et al., the object was then confirmed to be comoving with FW Tau, a close 0.2-0.3 M_{\odot} M5 binary in the Taurus-Auriga association (Bowler, et al., 2014). FW C/b was found to be unusually dim and red by the standards of analogous substellar objects, and later observations by ALMA detected an optically thin disk

with 1-2 M_{\oplus} of dust around the companion, which (depending on its inclination) may be causing significant extinction (Kraus, et al., 2014). While FW Tau C/b is theorized to have a mass on the order of $10M_J$ (Bowler, et al., 2014), the presence of this disk makes it difficult to constrain the luminosity and color, and with them the mass, of FW Tau C/b. As a result, it is difficult to determine the true nature of the PMC, which could either be a high-mass planetary object ("FW Tau b"), or a brown dwarf ("FW Tau C") with a heavily extinguishing edge-on disk.

2 Objectives

Our experiment consisted of simulating ALMA observations of FW Tau C/b's disk. Our goal was to show, through simulated observations of the system in varying possible setups, that accurate submillimeter observations could yield a precise dynamical mass for the PMC. This in turn would help resolve the question of whether FW Tau C/b is indeed a planet or a brown dwarf.

Obviously, such an observation would make a significant contribution to the nascent field of PMC astronomy, helping astronomers to better understand the nature of PMCs, and along with it to better grasp the mechanisms driving their formation. However, no non-transiting exoplanet or non-binary Brown Dwarf has yet had its mass measured to the degree of precision that a dynamical mass offers (Konopacky, et al., 2010); thus, accurately constraining the mass of FW Tau C/b would not only enhance our understanding of PMCs specifically, but also further contribute to other areas of substellar astronomy.

3 Methods

In preparing to carry out our simulation, we began by selecting two fiducial models to represent each of the two possible causes of FW Tau C/b's dimness and redness: either an edge-on disk with high column density extinguishing most of the light from a Brown Dwarf, or a more inclined disk and an intrinsically fainter (planetary) host object. In the "FW Tau C" (Brown Dwarf) case, M_c was simulated as $0.095 M_{\odot}$ and disk inclination as 85 degrees, while the disk temperature was approximated as 150 K. In the "FW Tau b" (planet) case, M_c was simulated as $.01 M_{\odot}$ and inclination as 60 degrees, and temperature as

130 K. In both models disk mass and radius were held constant at $5.0 \times 10^{-4} M_{\odot}$ and 20 AU respectively, based in part on the observations performed by Kraus, et al (2014). However, since these values are not well known, they were chosen largely as plausible but arbitrary values to be held constant from one case to the other. Our estimates of M_c and disk inclination were based on the models developed by Chabrier, et al. (2000).

Model	$M_c (M_{*})$	Inclination	Disk Mass (M_{*})	Disk Radius (AU)	Disk Temp (K)
FW Tau C	.095	85	5×10^{-4}	20	150
FW Tau b	.01	60	5×10^{-4}	20	130

Table 1: Representative parameters used in fiducial models.

These models were then created using the wrapper_GAS IDL script developed by Rosenfeld, et al. (2012) for use in analyzing the dynamical structure of disks. This script produces an precise spatially resolved model of CO emission from the J=2-1 rotational line across a number of velocity channels (in our case, 41), simulating how emission varies spatially and spectrally from a disk given the parameters of our fiducial models. CO was chosen despite the fact that molecular hydrogen is 10^4 times more abundant because of H₂'s lack of detectable emission lines.

Figure 1: 3D image of FW Tau C/b's disk, representing the Brown Dwarf fiducial model (central mass of $0.095 M_{\odot}$, inclination of 85 degrees, disk temperature 150 K).

Having produced fiducial simulations of FW Tau C/b and its disk, our next step was to produce moment maps and velocity spectra of the

simulated disk in IDL. While the moment maps, which illustrate spatially resolved velocities (weighted by line intensity) in the disk, were not of direct importance in terms of generating a dynamical mass, they do provide a useful means of visualizing the velocity field in FW Tau C/b’s disk, and of ensuring that our models made intuitive sense. The velocity spectra plotted flux over radial velocities, showing what velocities in the disk were responsible for the bulk of its emission. An ideal velocity spectrum (such as the one presented in figure 2) had a distinct ”two-pronged” shape, where the brightest regions of the disk on either side of the central mass were sufficiently differentiated to have a peak at both positive and negative velocities.

Figure 2: Velocity spectrum (a) and moment map (b) drawn from a wrapper_GAS data cube.

Since these models were indicative only of the conditions of the system itself, rather than observations of it, our next step was to simulate observations of FW Tau C/b and its disk in order to approximate real ALMA data. This was done using a CASA script called linescript.py, developed by Sean Andrews. The script took the data cube generated by wrapper_GAS and, in order to generate data representative of what ALMA observations would produce, took the fourier transform of each velocity channel and sampled only at the positions of antenna baselines. The script then reconstructed two image cubes, adding noise to one of the two. In simulating our observations we assumed an ALMA configuration called alma.out18, which is similar to ALMA’s expected configurations in the coming observation cycle. alma.out18 has long enough baselines to achieve the angular resolution necessary to observe the disk’s rotation pattern, but is not so widely spaced that it sacrifices spectral line sensitivity. The observations were centered on the CO J=2-1 rotational line at 230.458 GHz (accounting for spatial and spectral patterns caused by Keplerian rotation and Doppler shifting). Integration was simulated as 18,000 seconds across 41 velocity

channels, each 244 kHz wide, in order to maximize signal to noise and spectral resolution. Each iteration of the simulated observations produced two FITS data cubes, one including noise and one ignoring it.

Figure 3: Simulated ALMA observations of FW Tau C/b without and with sky noise (analogous to Figure 1).

Velocity spectra and moment maps were also generated in the "noisy" and noise-free cases in order to determine how accurately dynamical velocities in the disk could be measured in the presence of observation biases and sky noise.

Figure 4: Example of simulated velocity spectra of FW Tau C/b without and with sky noise (analogous to Figure 2a).

Having gone through this process for the fiducial cases representing a Brown Dwarf and a massive planet, we then repeated it with models with central masses offset by $\pm 50\%$ from each fiducial case, in order to demonstrate that observations would produce visibly different data as a result of relatively small changes in the mass of the observed PMC.

Figure 5: Example of simulated moment maps of FW Tau C/b without and with sky noise (analogous to Figure 2b).

4 Results

The results of our simulated observations are shown in figures 6 and 7. The difference between the Brown Dwarf and planet cases is immediately obvious, with far higher velocities (along with an obviously more inclined disk) in the case of the Brown Dwarf, and lower velocities and a less-inclined disk in the case of the planet. Line intensity is correspondingly higher in the planet case, and lower in the Brown Dwarf case.

Figure 6: Velocity spectra (left) and moment maps (right) of "FW Tau b" at simulated M_c of 0.005, 0.01, and 0.15 M_\odot . Velocities are shown to ± 0.75 km/s.

Due to the edge-on disk further increasing the magnitude of the disk material's radial velocity, the Brown Dwarf also sees a more obvious double peak in its velocity spectrum. While seeing this in actual observations of FW Tau C/b would both help to confirm that it is a Brown Dwarf and mean that getting a dynamical mass for the Brown Dwarf would be relatively straightforward, the fact that it is not seen in the lower-mass models does not mean that a precise dynamical mass would be unobtainable if FW Tau C/b were found to be a planet. In addition, while degeneracy does exist between mass and inclination, with higher mass and higher inclination having similar effects on line width, this is mitigated somewhat by the spatially resolved images and moment maps, which visibly reflect the difference in inclination between each case.

Figure 7: Velocity spectra (left) and moment maps (right) of "FW Tau C" at simulated M_c of 0.0475, 0.095, and 0.1425 M_\odot . Velocities are shown to ± 2 km/s.

It is worth noting that the velocity spectra and moment maps for the cases offset by $\pm 50\%$ in mass are markedly different from each other and from their respective fiducial models, showing that the data drawn from observations of a $.005 M_\odot$ planet would be significantly different from the data taken from observations of a $.01$ or $.015 M_\odot$ planet, even with the same disk inclination. If given the opportunity to conduct ALMA observations of FW Tau C/b, its mass could thus be inferred by generating a number of analogous models to these while

adjusting the unknown parameters of the system and performing a χ^2 fit to determine the mass specifically. This fitting process would also help to eliminate the ambiguity between high-mass, low-inclination and low-mass, high-inclination cases.

5 Conclusions

We have presented simulated ALMA observations centered on 230.538 GHz of two fiducial models of the 1-2 M_{\oplus} -disk surrounding FW Tau C/b, a wide (300 AU) planetary-mass companion to the close M5 binary FW Tau. Observations were simulated with an integration time of 18,000 seconds in the `alma.out18` configuration. Building on prior observations performed by Kraus, et al (2014) which confirmed FW Tau C/b's association with FW Tau and constrained its brightness, we assumed that the PMC could be simulated as either a $\approx 0.01 M_{\odot}$ planet with a disk inclined 60 degrees from face-on, or a $\approx .095 M_{\odot}$ Brown Dwarf with a heavily extinguishing disk inclined 85 degrees from face-on. The resultant data showed an obvious difference between higher-mass, higher-inclination models and lower-mass, lower-inclination models, and also differentiated between models at the same inclination which varied by a factor of 50% in mass. As such, our experiment clearly demonstrated the feasibility of using ALMA observations of FW Tau C/b's disk as a means of obtaining a dynamical mass for the PMC.

Such a mass would be crucial to determine whether FW Tau C/b is a Brown Dwarf or planet, and would thus be a significant step toward determining how wide-separation planetary-mass companions should be defined and how they are formed. Establishing its true nature, and knowing its mass to a high degree of precision, would add a valuable data point to both studies of planetary formation and stellar evolutionary models. Because of their extreme separations from their host stars, we are unlikely to ever discover a transiting PMC analogous to FW Tau C/b. As such, dynamical observations such as those simulated here are also likely to be the only means we will ever have of measuring the mass of a PMC.

Our hope is that, given the opportunity to perform in reality the observations simulated here, we will help to establish a precedent for the use of dynamical observations to obtain high-precision masses of disk-bearing objects. This in turn would greatly contribute to the body of knowledge surrounding protostellar and protoplanetary sys-

tems. Particularly when performed on wide-separation PMCs such as FW Tau C/b, such measurements would be a significant step forward in defining and revising our understanding of the distinction between a planet and a star.

It is worth noting that FW Tau's position within a star-forming region could complicate disk observations due to molecular gas in the field not associated with FW Tau C/b's disk. The density of this gas is not currently known (and was not accounted for in our simulations), but above a certain point it could obscure direct observations of CO emission in FW Tau C/b's disk. If given the chance, we plan to perform SMA observations of molecular gas surrounding FW Tau in order to assess the impact that this ambient material would have in order to factor it into our future observations of FW Tau C/b.

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